

Prophylactic Evaluation of Tramadol Hydrochloride and Pethidine Hydrochloride for Shivering in Patients undergoing Elective Surgery under Spinal Anaesthesia

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Abstract

Introduction: Shivering is one of the most common complications during spinal anesthesia, leading to patient discomfort and increased metabolic demand. This is a result of blocked sympathetic activity with effective vasodilatation, leading to loss of thermoregulation. This study aimed to compare the efficacy of prophylactic pethidine and tramadol in preventing shivering in patients undergoing spinal anesthesia.

Aims and Objective: To analyze the outcome of prophylactic Tramadol hydrochloride and Pethidine hydrochloride for shivering patients who underwent elective surgery under spinal anaesthesia.

Method: This prospective, randomized double blinded study, was conducted in 120 ASA 1 and ASA 2 adult patients of either gender scheduled for elective surgery and spinal anaesthesia.

Patients were allocated into 2 groups of 30 each, to receive either pethidine or tramadol in a dose of 0.5mg/kg 10 min before administration of spinal anaesthesia. Intraoperative hemodynamic Parameters, incidence and severity of shivering were recorded and statistically analysed with t-tests, chi-square tests and ANOVAs.

Result: The incidence and severity of shivering was significantly lower in pethidine group compared to tramadol group ($p < 0.001$). However, pethidine is associated with mild sedation score and lower incidence of nausea and vomiting compared to tramadol.

Conclusion: Prophylactic pethidine is more effective than tramadol in reducing the incidence and severity of shivering with minimal sedation in patients undergoing elective infra umbilical surgery under spinal anaesthesia.

Keywords: Pethidine, Tramadol, Spinal Anaesthesia, Shivering.

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Introduction

Shivering is defined as involuntary, repetitive activity in the skeletal muscles. It is a common concern encountered during spinal anaesthesia.[1] Shivering is a physiological response to core hypothermia in an attempt to increase the metabolic heat production. An incidence of shivering of up to 55% has been reported earlier.[2]. Spinal anaesthesia significantly impairs the thermoregulation system causing vasodilation, which facilitates rapid heat loss and redistribution of body heat from core to periphery. causing hypothermia and renders to shivering.[3]

Preoptic nucleus of hypothalamus perceive hypothermia and initiates protective mechanism against cold.[4] Although shivering is not a life threatening process it can be a source of patient discomfort and may interfere with the monitoring of ECG, blood pressure and pulse oxygen saturation

[5]. It can also have deleterious metabolic and cardiovascular effect such as increased cardiac activity, elevated oxygen consumption and carbon dioxide production [6,7]. It also increases intracranial and intraocular pressure, escalates postoperative pain, delay wound healing, and detain discharge from post anaesthesia care [8,9].

Therefore, shivering should ideally be prohibited or treated by pharmacological and nonpharmacological method. Several pharmacologic approaches have been reported serving as preventive or therapeutic measures for shivering cause by spinal anaesthesia. The most frequent pharmacological interventions include pethidine and tramadol.[10]

Pethidine is an opioid derivative, and its mechanism is likely to be associated with the activation of κ and μ -opioid receptor, acting principally on the central

nervous system. It is an agonist at both the μ and κ receptors closely related to the pathogenesis of shivering by reducing the shivering threshold and triggering decreased core temperature, which constitutes its anti-shivering effect. [11]

Tramadol is a synthetic opioid that acts at multiple sites. It is a weak μ -opioid receptor agonist and has minimal activity at κ - or σ -receptors. It is also a partial inhibitor of norepinephrine and 5-hydroxytryptamine (5HT) and facilitates serotonin release. Each of these actions is likely to influence thermoregulatory control. [12]

In evaluating the prophylactic use of Tramadol and Pethidine to prevent shivering during spinal anesthesia we have not only looked at the effectiveness in terms of the incidence and extent of shivering but also at the side effects of these drugs and their overall effects on patients.

Method

Research Design: This prospective double blinded randomized controlled study was conducted on patients undergoing elective infraumbilical surgeries under spinal anesthesia at the Tertiary Care Hospital Bangalore, Karnataka for a time period of August 2022 to August 2024. The consent from patients along with approval from ethical committee of the hospital were taken. Patients who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Pre anesthetic examination was done for each patient including complete blood picture, renal function tests, liver function tests, coagulation profile. Patients were premedicated with 0.25 mg tablet Alprazolam on the night preceding the surgery.

On the day of surgery upon arrival in operation theatre 18 gauze cannula was inserted in the dorsal aspect of either hand. Standard non invasive monitors were used to record the heart rate, mean arterial pressure, and peripheral oxygen saturation before administration of spinal anaesthesia. Vitals were monitored at intervals of 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 40, 50 minutes until the end of the surgery. Body temperature was continuously monitored using a mercurial thermometer, measurements were taken in the axilla to ensure accurate monitoring of body temperature. Operation theatre temperature was maintained between 21-23 degree celsius.

A specific formula was used for calculation of sample size –

$$\eta = \left[\frac{z1 - \frac{\alpha}{2\sqrt{(r+1)P(1-P)}} + Z1 - \beta \sqrt{r(p1(1-p1) + p2(1-p2))}}{r(p2-p1)^2} \right]^2$$

where,

$$P = p1 + rp2 / 1 + r$$

Z=Standard normal variable

A= 0.05 level of significance

r = group size ratio

β = 0.2 power of test

p1= incidence of shivering in tramadol group 50%

p2= incidence of shivering in pethidine group 50%

Patients were randomly allocated in 2 groups group P and T based on computer generated random numbers each possessing 30 patients. They received injection Tramadol or Pethidine 0.5mg/kg intravenously diluted in 10 ml of normal saline and administered over 10 minutes.

The study drugs were injected 10 minutes before the administration of spinal anesthesia. Intraoperatively all patients were covered with the surgical drape over the chest, thighs, and calves, and with a cotton blanket over the entire body post-operation.

Shivering was monitored and graded using the Crossley and Mahajan five point scale. If shivering occurred it was graded, recorded and treated with antishivering agent. Persistent shivering for 15 minutes at grade 3 or above was treated with a second dose of the same drug. Sedation was graded by a 5 point ordinal scale. Side effects like nausea and vomiting were observed and treated with injection ondansetron 4 mg intravenously.

Inclusion criteria

- Written informed consent for the study
- ASA physical status of class I and II.
- Aged > 18 years.
- Patients undergoing elective infraumbilical surgery under spinal anesthesia.

Exclusion criteria

- Neuromuscular diseases.
- Psychological disorders or use of psychotropic drugs.
- Diagnosed case of Hypothyroidism / hyperthyroidism or cardiopulmonary diseases, history of convulsion were excluded
- from the study.
- Body temperature greater than 38.0°C or less than 35 °C were excluded from the study
- Recent history of febrile illness
- History of alcohol intake and substance abuse / vasodilators.
- Patients with history of intraoperative blood transfusion.
- Allergic to Pethidine/Tramadol
- Pregnant patients.

- Contraindications to central neuraxial blockade.
- Patients with sensory block < T8 level, fifteen minutes after Subarachnoid Block or having > 6 VAS pain score intraoperatively.

Results

Statistical analysis: The study has used SPSS 27 for

effective analysis and MS Excel was used to calculate the frequency and percentages as required. All the data which was collected was analyzed and recorded using different tests which includes mean and standard deviation, T test, chi-square test along with ANOVA (Analysis of variance) which is used for analysis of repeated measures.

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of the patients in pethidine and tramadol group

characteristics	Pethidine n=30	Tramadol n=30	P value
Age (years) (mean ± SD)	57.1 ± 18.5	51.9 ± 21.3	0.068
Male, n (%)	14 (46.7%)	17 (56.7%)	0.51
Female, n (%)	16 (53.3%)	13 (43.3%)	
Body Weight (kg) (mean ± SD)	76.0 ± 13.8	78.6 ± 14.1	0.847
Height (cm) (mean ± SD)	167.7 ± 13.0	168.7 ± 12.4	0.538
BMI (mean ± SD)	27.1 ± 6.2	27.6 ± 6.6	
ASA Physical Status, n (%)			0.796
I	23 (76.7%)	26 (86.7%)	0.891
II	7 (23.3%)	4 (13.3%)	
Baseline Heart Rate (bpm)	80.6 ± 10.6	81.3 ± 11.5	0.56
Baseline MAP (mmHg)	90.6 ± 12.1	88.6 ± 12.0	0.894
Baseline SpO ₂ (%)	97.5 ± 1.5	97.4 ± 1.6	0.938
Baseline Body Temperature (°C)	36.8 ± 0.4	36.8±0.4	0.774

Table 1 shows the baseline characteristics of patients receiving pethidine (n=30) and tramadol (n=30) were compared. The average age was slightly higher in the pethidine group (57.1 ± 18.5 years) compared to the tramadol group (51.9 ± 21.3 years), but this difference was not statistically significant (p = 0.068). The gender distribution was similar between the two groups, with 46.7% males and 53.3% females in the pethidine group, and 56.7% males and 43.3% females in the tramadol group (p = 0.51). The mean body weight and height were also comparable, with a mean weight of 76.0 ± 13.8 kg in the pethidine group and 78.6 ± 14.1 kg in the tramadol group

(p = 0.847), and mean height of 167.7 ± 13.0 cm in the pethidine group versus 168.7 ± 12.4 cm in the tramadol group (p = 0.538). BMI values were similar (27.1 ± 6.2 in pethidine group and 27.6 ± 6.6 in tramadol group). ASA physical status distribution showed no significant difference (p = 0.796), with most patients classified as ASA I (76.7% for pethidine and 86.7% for tramadol). Baseline heart rate, mean arterial pressure (MAP), SpO₂, and body temperature were all closely matched between the groups, with p-values of 0.56, 0.894, 0.938, and 0.774, respectively, indicating no significant differences.

Table 2: Types of surgery and the clinical characteristics of the two groups

Characteristics	Pethidine n=30	Tramadol n=30	P value
Type of Surgery			
Hernia Repair	9 (30.0%)	9 (30.0%)	0.99
Hysterectomy	11 (36.7%)	11 (36.7%)	
Appendectomy	10 (33.3%)	10 (33.3%)	
Duration of Surgery (minutes)	116.0 ± 41.7	106.8 ± 43.9	0.859

Table 2 shows the types of surgeries performed were evenly distributed between the two groups, with no significant differences in the frequencies of hernia repair (30% in both groups, p = 0.99), hysterectomy (36.7% in both groups), and appendectomy (33.3% in both groups). The duration of surgery was also

comparable, with a mean duration of 116.0 ± 41.7 minutes in the pethidine group and 106.8 ± 43.9 minutes in the tramadol group (p = 0.859), suggesting no significant difference in the length of procedures between the group.

Table 3: Findings related to intraoperative characteristics of the two groups

Characteristics	Pethidine n=30	Tramadol n=30	P value
Intraoperative Fluid Administration (ml)	1300±327	1226.7±457.6	0.063
Sensory Block Level	30(100%)	30(100%)	1
VAS Pain Score Intraoperatively	3.0±1	3.0±1	0.071
Operating Room Temperature	22.1±0.6	22.1±0.6	0.931

During the surgery, intraoperative fluid administration was slightly higher in the pethidine group (1300 ± 327 ml) compared to the tramadol group (1226.7 ± 457.6 ml), but this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.063$). The sensory block level achieved was identical between both groups, with all patients (100%) achieving the required level

($p = 1$). The Visual Analog Scale (VAS) pain scores recorded intraoperatively were the same for both groups (3.0 ± 1), with no significant difference ($p = 0.071$). The operating room temperature was consistently maintained at $22.1 \pm 0.6^\circ\text{C}$ for both groups ($p = 0.931$), indicating no variation in environmental conditions during surgery (Table 3).

Table 4: Incidence of shivering and Sedation Score of the patients in each group

Characteristics	Pethidine n=30	Tramadol n=30	P value
Incidence of shivering			
Yes	12 (40%)	14 (46.7%)	<0.001
No	18 (60%)	16 (53.3%)	
Grade of shivering n(%)			
0	18 (60%)	16 (53.3%)	<0.05
1	6 (20%)	7 (23.3%)	
2	4 (13.3%)	3 (10%)	
3	2 (6.7%)	3 (10%)	
4	0 (0%)	1 (3.3%)	
Duration of Shivering (minute, mean ± SD)			
	12.7 ± 8.4	13.7±8.1	
second dose required(for grade 3 and grade 4), n(%)			
yes	2 (6.7%)	4 (13.3%)	<0.05
No	28 (93.3%)	26 (86.7%)	
Sedation score			
Grade 0	15 (50%)	22 (73.3%)	0.0001
Grade 1	12 (40%)	6 (20%)	
Grade 2	3 (10%)	2 (6.7%)	
Grade 3	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Grade 4	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	

There was a statistically significant difference in the incidence of shivering between the two groups, with 40% of patients in the pethidine group experiencing shivering compared to 46.7% in the tramadol group ($p < 0.001$). The grades of shivering were also significantly different between the groups ($p < 0.05$), with more severe grades observed slightly more frequently in the tramadol group. The duration of shivering was similar, with mean durations of 12.7 ± 8.4 minutes in the pethidine group and 13.7 ± 8.1 minutes in the tramadol group. The need for a second dose, particularly for grade 3 and 4 shivering, was more common in the tramadol group (13.3%)

compared to the pethidine group (6.7%), with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). Regarding sedation scores, a significantly higher proportion of patients in the tramadol group had a grade 0 sedation score (73.3%) compared to the pethidine group (50%) ($p = 0.0001$). This shows that pethidine has more sedative effect as compared to tramadol. Table 4 shows the detailed findings.

Figure 1 – 5 Heart rate, respiratory rate, body temperature, mean arterial pressure and Spo2 are measured for different time intervals from 0 to 120 minutes for the two group

Figure 1: Body temperature

The body temperature remained relatively stable for both the pethidine and tramadol groups over the 120-minute observation period. In the pethidine group, body temperature started at 36.29°C and slightly fluctuated, reaching a minimum of 36.03°C at 15 minutes and a maximum of 36.40°C at 120 minutes.

In the tramadol group, the temperature began at 36.29°C and remained fairly consistent, with minor fluctuations between 35.98°C at 10 minutes and 36.34°C at 40 and 50 minutes. Overall, the body temperature changes were minimal in both groups, with no significant deviations observed (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Respiratory Rate

The respiratory rate showed mild variation over time for both groups. In the pethidine group, the rate initially decreased from 16 ± 2.9 breaths per minute to a minimum of 13 ± 2.7 breaths per minute at 20 minutes, then gradually increased back to 16 breaths per minute by 120 minutes. In contrast, the tramadol group had a relatively stable respiratory rate

throughout, starting at 15.4 ± 2.7 breaths per minute and showing only slight variations, maintaining around 15-16 breaths per minute for most of the period. The variations in respiratory rates between the two groups were minimal, with a slightly more stable trend in the tramadol group (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Heart rate

The heart rate exhibited modest fluctuations across the observation period for both groups. In the pethidine group, the heart rate started at 80.4 ± 12.3 bpm and generally decreased to a low of 76 ± 11.3 bpm at 20 minutes before stabilizing around 80-81 bpm towards the end of the observation period. In the

tramadol group, the heart rate began at 78.9 ± 10.7 bpm, dropped to 77.7 ± 9.8 bpm at 10 minutes, and then slightly increased, maintaining around 80-82 bpm toward the end. The trends suggest that the heart rates in both groups were largely similar, with no significant changes over time (Figure 3).

Figure 4: Mean Arterial Pressure

Mean arterial pressure was relatively stable in both groups, with minor variations. For the pethidine group, MAP started at 90.2 ± 11.5 mmHg, fluctuated slightly between 82 ± 11.4 mmHg at 15 minutes and 90 ± 11.6 mmHg at 100 minutes. In the tramadol group, MAP began at 89.5 ± 10.3 mmHg, showed

small fluctuations between 88.5 ± 10.3 mmHg at 40 minutes and 89 ± 11.2 mmHg at 100 minutes. Overall, both groups maintained stable MAP readings throughout the observation period. Oxygen saturation (SpO2) levels were consistently high in both groups throughout the observation period (Figure 4).

Figure 5: oxygen saturation

In the pethidine group, SpO2 levels started at $97.3 \pm 1.3\%$ and showed minor variations, peaking at 98% at 60 and 80 minutes. In the tramadol group, SpO2 began at $97.2 \pm 1.2\%$ and remained stable around 97-98% throughout the period. The high consistency in SpO2 values indicates no significant changes or differences between the two groups (Figure 5).

The study suggests that minimal variation in all

measured parameters (body temperature, respiratory rate, heart rate, MAP, and SpO2) over time in both the pethidine and tramadol groups. There were no significant differences between the two groups in the trends of these parameters, indicating that both medications maintained similar physiological stability in patients throughout the observation period (Figure 1).

Table 4: Incidence of Nausea and Vomiting and Pruritis in the patients of each group

Adverse Event	Pethidine n=30	Tramadol n=30	P value
Nausea and Vomiting	2 (6.67%)	16 (53.3%)	<0.001
Pruritis	0	0	

The results presented in Table 4 indicate a significant difference in the incidence of adverse events, particularly nausea and vomiting, between the pethidine and tramadol groups. None of the patients in the pethidine group (2 out of 30) experienced nausea or vomiting, while 53.3% of the patients in the tramadol group (16 out of 30) reported these side effects. This difference was statistically significant, with a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating that tramadol is associated with a much higher incidence of nausea and vomiting compared to pethidine. Additionally, there were no recorded cases of pruritis (itching) in either group, suggesting that neither pethidine nor tramadol caused this adverse effect in the patient population studied.

These findings suggest that tramadol may lead to a higher occurrence of nausea and vomiting while pethidine does not appear to provoke such adverse events in study group.

Discussion

Spinal anesthesia is the most common technique used for elective infraumbilical surgeries. However, it is associated with adverse effects like hypotension, bradycardia, shivering, nausea and vomiting. Sympathetic blockade resulting from spinal anesthesia leads to vasodilation and that shifts blood from the central to peripheral regions. These changes leads to severe heat loss and decrease in the core body temperature in turn lead to hypothermia [3]. Compensatory mechanisms like shivering occurs to restore body temperature to normal level. Minimizing shivering in patients undergoing elective surgery under spinal anaesthesia is one of the major concerns during the surgical period because it increases cardiac activity, oxygen consumption, and carbon dioxide production [6,7]. These effects are deleterious for cardiac patients. Shivering also increases intracranial and intraocular pressure, escalates postoperative pain, delay wound healing, and detain discharge from post anaesthesia care [8,9].

Hence, a prevention of shivering is imperative to keeping intra-operative conditions as stable as possible, in order to keep patients comfortable and safe [7, 9, 12, 15, 18].

Many drugs have been used in pharmacologic interventions to either prevent or treat shivering that occurs with spinal anesthesia such as opioids (tramadol, pethidine); alpha 2 agonist

(dexmedetomidine, clonidine); cholinesterase inhibitors (physostigmine); corticosteroids (dexamethasone, hydrocortisone); antiserotonergic (ondansetron) and NMDA receptor antagonist (ketamine) [2]. From the above methods, Opioid like Tramadol hydrochloride and Pethidine hydrochloride has proven to yield the most positive results. These drugs influence central thermoregulatory mechanisms to control the response to cold stimuli and thereby preventing shivering. As a result, both Tramadol and Pethidine are often promoted for preemptive prescription in patients undergoing elective surgical procedures under spinal anesthesia [6, 8, 22].

Tramadol hydrochloride a centrally acting analgesic drug is effective in post anaesthetic shivering after general and neuraxial anaesthesia. It is a weak μ -opioid receptor agonist and has minimal activity at κ - or σ -receptors. [2] It inhibits the reuptake of 5-hydroxy tryptamine (5HT) and noradrenaline, facilitates 5HT release and activates μ -opioid receptor. Each of these actions is likely to influence thermoregulatory control [10, 13, 14, 17, 23, 24]

Pethidine hydrochloride is an opioid derivative, and its mechanism is likely to be associated with the activation of κ and μ -opioid receptor, acting principally on the central nervous system. It is an agonist at both the μ and κ receptors closely related to the pathogenesis of shivering by reducing the shivering threshold and triggering decreased core temperature, which constitutes its anti-shivering effect. [11]

In our study, we found statistically significant differences in the incidence of shivering between the two groups, with 40% of patients in the pethidine group experiencing shivering compared to 46.7% in the tramadol group ($p < 0.001$). The grades of shivering were also significantly different between the groups ($p < 0.05$), with more severe grades observed slightly more frequently in the tramadol group. The need for a second dose, particularly for grade 3 and 4 shivering, was more common in the tramadol group (13.3%) compared to the pethidine group (6.7%), with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Regarding sedation scores, a significantly higher proportion of patients in the tramadol group had a grade 0 sedation score (73.3%) compared to the pethidine group (50%) ($p = 0.0001$). This shows that pethidine has more sedative effect as compared to

tramadol.

Conclusion

The study concluded that both the pethidine and tramadol maintain similar physiological stability in patients during surgery, as indicated by consistent measurements of body temperature, respiratory rate, heart rate, mean arterial pressure, and oxygen saturation over time. However, tramadol is associated with a higher incidence and severity of shivering, while pethidine has a stronger sedative effect. Hence, we conclude, Prophylactic pethidine is more effective than tramadol in reducing the incidence and severity of shivering with minimal sedation in patients undergoing elective infra umbilical surgery under spinal anesthesia.

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